

Premenstrual Dysphoric Disorder in higher education: exploring the impact of menstrual mental health on academic professionals

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Indicate your track: Institutional interventions and policies

Purpose

Menstrual health is public health and a human rights issue. Women make up 50% of the world's population, of which, nearly 26% menstruate. On any given day, about 300 million women menstruate worldwide. Over 90% of menstruators experience some grade of PMS (premenstrual symptoms) like bloating, cramps, migraines, dizziness and moodiness. About 10% of these women experience a more severe form of PMS known as Premenstrual Dysphoric Disorder (PMDD) and/or Premenstrual Exacerbation (PME) of existing conditions. The current study aims to explore the impact of PMDD on women and people assigned female at birth, in higher education.

Premenstrual Dysphoric Disorder is a menstrual-related mood disorder affecting 5.5-8% of females of reproductive age (IAPMD.org). Clinically categorised as a mental disorder in the DSM-5, PMDD is characterised by debilitating psychological symptoms in the luteal phase of the menstrual cycle (1-2 weeks before menstruation), which dissipate with the onset of menses. Symptoms include: cyclical depression, anxiety, brain fog, fatigue, dizziness, irritability, self-harm behaviours and suicidal ideation. Alongside these psychological symptoms, women may also experience physical symptoms such as insomnia, fatigue or bloating. 1 in 3 women with PMDD will attempt suicide in their lifetime; 51% of patients have a history of self-harm and 72% experience suicidal ideation ([Eisenlohr-Moul et al., 2022](#)).

PMDD has a significant negative impact on education and work. Recent research has found that people with PMDD frequently drop out of university or opt for 'less-demanding' jobs, often losing out on skills, opportunities and financial stability ([Matthews, 2023](#)).

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The magnitude of PMDD and its effect on work performance and life quality of female academics ([Tsegaye & Getachew, 2019](#)) and medical students ([Maity et al., 2022](#)) has been reported in several peer-reviewed publications.

There is a huge gap between the prevalence and impact of PMDD and available support, either via medical management or via university-led initiatives. Academic institutions lack special considerations and policies to accommodate the needs of their menstruating students and staff. This warrants urgent awareness and sustained institutional intervention to support and retain female researchers with PMDD, and encourage them to achieve their personal and academic potential.

Design

The proposed study in conjunction with European Universities (including the University Of The West of Scotland) aims to explore: (1) the impact of chronic menstrual mental health issues (like PMDD and PME) on the mental well-being of female (menstruating) researchers; (2) how researchers navigate their workload around their menstrual medical conditions; and (3) what strategies can be adopted by academic institutions to support researchers with these conditions.

We will hold focus groups, individual interviews and surveys to gather insight from researchers and academic stakeholders, such as Occupational Health personnel, Human Resources, and student and staff well-being services. Together with stakeholders, we will create a manifesto with recommendations on how academic institutions can better support researchers with menstrual mental health disorders.

Alongside this research, we will promote menstrual mental health support with ongoing stakeholder engagement events. We will hold workshops and seminars for researchers and relevant stakeholders to increase education and awareness around menstruation, and associated physiological and psychological issues. By doing this, we aim to empower researchers to effectively communicate their needs around their menstrual health- both within and outside universities, and encourage stakeholders to take appropriate action.

Some of our preliminary surveys also revealed 'hesitation and lack of knowledge' of male counterparts in discussing menstrual (and/or menopausal) matters. To address these societal

facets, we will conduct workshops focussing on education and breaking gender barriers around menstrual issues and creating a safe space for gathering information and learning techniques to better support colleagues, friends and family. We are keen to collaborate with other European COST and ITC countries, and welcome dialogue with interested researchers.

Implications of the research

Findings from this research will help to promote an understanding of researchers' needs around their menstrual cycles and PMDD. Practical recommendations will enable universities to provide appropriate support to researchers struggling with menstrual mental health and associated issues. Long-term, this will positively impact the quality of work/life/health balance, increase retention of researchers in academia and decrease the frequency of sickness absence. Breaking taboos, championing true inclusivity and making tangible policy changes around menstrual matters is only possible when all gender and stakeholder groups interact openly and respectfully.

Collectively, academic institutions and mental health-focused organisations like ReMO have the potential (and responsibility) to be the change-makers and contribute to increasing education, awareness, empathy and inclusivity around hidden disabilities like PMDD within universities and society, at large.

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